

Engineering the Fairness of Blackjack

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Abstract

Blackjack is a popular card game and is a widely played casino banking game. To win the blackjack, the players aim at getting a higher total value of the cards than the dealer, while not exceeding 21. The current rule of blackjack allows the players to know one card from the dealer and draw any number of cards randomly until they choose to stop. While the dealer must continue to take cards until the total value is 17 or more. In the gambling industry, the house edge in a game such as blackjack may be high to favor the casino. Despite many previous studies on the player's optimal strategy, little research was conducted on investigating the fairness of the blackjack. Thus, in this study, we aimed at investigating whether the current rule of blackjack is fair or not and how rule modifications impact the fairness of blackjack. Using probability theory, an optimal player's strategy of when to stop drawing additional cards was proposed and the corresponding fairness was assessed by the player's expected odd of winning. The optimal strategy was found to be affected by the dealer's up card. Meanwhile, we also derived fairness when the rules are modified, such as changing the minimum total value of cards that the dealers must stop drawing cards. These theoretical derivations were verified against numerical simulations. The sensitivity of the fairness with rule modifications was discussed. Finally, we proposed a few ways of rule modifications to further improve the fairness of the blackjack.

1 Introduction

Blackjack is a popular yet simple kind of card game based on playing cards. Players need to get higher total value of cards without exceeding 21. Players can choose to draw cards to increase their value until they stop, but they also need to consider the possibility to exceed 21. Therefore, they need to compare the reward and drawback of drawing a new card before making their own decision. However, since many people have studied about its strategies, this paper will study how modifying its rules will affect fairness.

Since many researchers have analyzed strategy of player in several ways, including Nash Equilibrium [Mu20] and method of exhaustion [Wor18], few researchers tried to modify the rules and change the action of the dealer. In this paper, I will talk about several ways of modifying the rules and the corresponding effect on fairness.

In this paper, the Blackjack game will be illustrated first to clarify the background of this study. Then, a strategy is derived, which is the best strategy under some assumptions. After that, based on the strategy, two different modifications on the rule will be discussed, and their relationship with fairness of the game will be found.

2 The game of Blackjack

2.1 What is Blackjack

Blackjack is a game based on playing cards. It uses several sets, usually 8, of playing cards without the jokers. On one single table, there will be one dealer and several players. For both the dealers and players, the ultimate goal is to get a higher total value of cards while not exceeding 21.

In this game, different card has different value. Number cards (2-10) have same value as their number. J, Q, and Ks have the value of 10. A usually has the value of 11, but if the total value is greater than 21, it becomes 1.

When the game starts, the dealer will get two cards, one face-up and one face-down. Then, each player can do their own actions, which will be discussed in the next section. If the total value of a player exceeds 21, which is called "bust", that player will immediately lose the game. When all players are finished, the dealer will reveal all cards and draw cards until the value becomes at least 17. If the dealer busts, all remaining players win. If not, the player with the higher total value wins, with a lower total value loses, and with the same value draws.

2.2 Player decisions

In each player's turn, the player can do the following actions any number of times in any order until they bust, choose to stand, or choose to double.

1. Hit: take an additional card
2. Stand: take no more cards
3. Double down: double the bet (so lose double money and win double money), but hit only one more card, and then stand.
4. Split: If the first two cards have the same value, the player can split these cards into two piles and behave like two players. The two piles will be totally independent.
5. Surrender: before doing any actions above, any player may decide to surrender and return half his bet

2.3 Modifications of rules

In this paper I will discuss two modifications of rules and their corresponding results on fairness:

1. Change the number of face-up cards of the dealer
2. Change the range of the value in which the dealer must stand

However, before discussing the modification in rules, a reasonable strategy must be found. In the next section, I will find the best strategy under some assumptions (which is the best strategy in most of the cases), and determine fairness based on the expected gain of a player using such strategy.

3 Player strategy

In this section, I will talk about the best strategy under the assumptions above. Since the action is restricted to either hit or stand, the goal of this section is only to find the range of values in which it is better to stand.[\[RRB56\]](#)

To simplify the question, I assume that all cards have equal probability of being drawn. It means that each new card is drawn from a brand new deck, rather than from an incomplete deck. Therefore, there is no need to determine what cards are left in the deck, and also no need to record the drawn cards individually.

Also, the strategy below includes only hit and stand. Other actions like splitting will make the problem too complex to discuss the rule modifications below.

3.1 Soft hands

With the assumption that every card has equal possibility to be drawn, only the total value matters. For example, if the total value of a hand is 11, whether it is a combination of 2 + 9 or a combination of 3 + 8, the strategy is always the same. However, card "A" is a special card in Blackjack, since its value can be either 1 or 11. With an "A" representing 11 in a hand, no matter what the next card is, this hand will never bust after the next hit. Such hand is called a "soft hand". Accordingly, a hand without an "A" or with a "A" representing 1 is called a "hard hand". Since they have different possibilities of bust, the strategy modifies.

3.2 Strategy for hard hands

Since the strategy for soft hands depends on two different hard hands, hard hands should be discussed first. First of all, let us define the expected gain E . Assume that if the player wins, that player gains 1. Accordingly, if that player loses, he gains -1, and when draw it is 0. Then, let us define a random variable T , which is the final value of the dealer, and a variable L , which is the final value of the player. Since the dealer always stand at 17 or more, when $L < 17$,

$$E_l = P(T > 21) - P(17 \leq T \leq 21) \quad (1)$$

Where E_l represents the expected gain of player when the value of the player equals l . Obviously, according to the basic rule, when the player busts, or $L > 21$,

$$E_l = -1 \quad (2)$$

For the remaining situation, when $17 \leq L \leq 21$, the result depends on their values, so

$$E_l = P(T > 21) + P(L > T) - P(L < T) \quad (3)$$

To calculate the E_l above, the only known information in a Blackjack game is the revealed card from the dealer. Let us define the value of that card D , and the total value of dealer with shown card D , $M(D)$. Therefore, for any $n > 11$,

$$P(M(D) = n) = \sum_{i=n-11}^{n-1} P(M(D) = i)P(c = n - i) \quad (4)$$

and for any $n \leq 11$,

$$P(M(D) = n) = \sum_{i=2}^{n-1} P(M(D) = i)P(c = n - i) \quad (5)$$

Where c is a random variable representing the value of the next drawn card. Using simple recursive algorithm to apply these equations, a table is made through programming, showing the probability of standing at each value for the dealer with the value of the shown card D :

Table of possibility of standing value of the dealer

final $M(D)$	17	18	19	20	21	bust
$D=2$.141781	.134885	.131432	.123829	.119581	.348492
$D=3$.133533	.133052	.126197	.122563	.114903	.369751
$D=4$.132206	.116037	.122553	.117930	.114292	.396983
$D=5$.121374	.124511	.117753	.105446	.107823	.423092
$D=6$.167625	.107233	.108018	.101260	.098364	.417499
$D=7$.372743	.139017	.077841	.079409	.073437	.257552
$D=8$.131202	.363359	.129634	.068457	.070026	.237322
$D=9$.122256	.104217	.357550	.122256	.061079	.232643
$D=10$.114756	.113186	.114756	.328873	.114755	.213674
$D=(1,11)$.128147	.131284	.129716	.131284	.365009	.114560

With such a table we are able to calculate the expectation. Therefore, to determine whether to hit or stand, we only need to calculate the two expectations and compare them. Before discussing that, we need to find special cases first. For all $L \leq 11$, since there is no risk of bust and hitting will always increase the total value, the best strategy is always hit. For $L = 21$, since there is no chance of getting higher value without bust, the best strategy is always stand. For $12 \leq L < 21$, we need to compare the expected gain of stand, E_l , and the expected gain of hit,

$$H_l = \sum_{i=l+1}^{l+10} P(c = i - n)E_l \quad (6)$$

With such equation, the strategy list can be made by programming using Monte Carlo sampling:

- For $2 \leq D \leq 3$: stand at $l \geq 13$
- For $4 \leq D \leq 6$: stand at $l \geq 12$
- For $7 \geq D$ and $D = (1, 11)$: stand at $l \geq 17$

3.3 Strategy for soft hands

Similarly, a soft hand can be considered as two hard hands. Let us define the expected gain of a soft hand with total value after hitting S_l . Since for $L < 17$ there is no risk of bust, and E_l remains unchanged if the total value decreases, the best strategy is always hit. For $L \geq 17$,

$$S_l = \sum_{i=l+1}^{21} P(c = i - n)E_l + \sum_{i=12}^l P(c = i + 10 - n)H_l \quad (7)$$

With such equation, the strategy list can be made by programming:

- For $D \leq 8$ and $D = (1, 11)$: stand at $l \geq 18$
- For $D \geq 9$: stand at $l \geq 19$

4 Changing the number of revealing cards

In the rule of Blackjack, the revealed card provides useful information and affect the best strategy greatly. In this section, the Blackjack game without this rule will be discussed, and since the strategy is simplified, the disadvantage will be found.

4.1 Expected gain in the original Blackjack game

With strategy determined above, the expected gain can be determined through method of exhaustion. The table below shows the relationship of expected gain of player, E , with all values of the revealed card, D :

Table of expected gain of players

D	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	(1,11)
E	.090	.123	.167	.218	.230	.148	.056	-.043	-.176	-.363

With such table, considering the probability of each D , the overall expected gain is -0.006.

4.2 Expected gain in the modified Blackjack game

In this section, we assume that the player always stand at $L \geq 17$ and always hit at $L \leq 16$, which is the most common case in the overall best strategy.

Using the table of the possibility of dealer values in 3.2, we need to ignore the condition of D to make it more general using the equation:

$$P(M(D) = n) = \sum_{i=2}^{11} P(M(D) = n|D = i)P(c = i) \quad (8)$$

And this equation creates the table below:

Table of standing value of the dealer in the original game

final $M(D)$	17	18	19	20	21	bust
possibility	.140391	.140145	.139302	.143865	.135655	.300642

Since the player in this situation uses the same strategy as the dealer, the table for dealer and player are the same. According to formula (1),(2) and (3), the expected gain for player is -.090. This action affect the expected gain of the player by -0.084. It fits the intuition that hiding information will give advantage to the dealer.

Figure 1: This figure shows the possibility of standing values under different rules

5 Changing the dealer strategy

In this section, I assume that the player strategy will not be affected by the modifications of dealer strategy.

Since it is unclear how increasing the value at which the dealer must stand will affect the expected gain of player, here I will explore it in both ways: increasing and decreasing. Both numbers 16 and 18 will be tested. Using method of exhaustion, if the dealer stands at $M(D) \geq 16$,

Table of standing value of the dealer in the modified game 1

final $M(D)$	16	17	18	19	20	21	bust
possibility	.130787	.131134	.1308584	.129917	.135014	.125843	.216446

and if the dealer stands at $M(D) \geq 18$,

Table of standing value of the dealer in the modified game 2

final $M(D)$	18	19	20	21	bust
possibility	.150227	.149459	.153620	.146133	.400560

With data above, the expected gain for the player can be calculated using formula (1),(2) and (3). Take $E = -0.090$ as a standard, when the dealer stands at 16, $E = -0.241$, and when the dealer stands at 18, $E = -0.063$. When that number decreases by 1, the expected gain decreases by 0.131, while when it increases by 1 the expected gain increases by 0.027. Therefore, around the value 17, increase in that number will increase the expected gain, and it decreases faster than it increases.

Comparing these numbers to the result in section 4, the relationship of sensitivity is also found: By decreasing the value the dealer stands, the sensitivity is much greater. The sensitivity for showing cards is also sensitive, while increasing the value the dealer stands is not a sensitive modification.

6 Conclusion

This paper discusses two kinds of rule modifications under a simple Blackjack game that can be studied using Monte Carlo sampling. However, this model is too simple with many assumptions. For example, in a real Blackjack game, players have actions other than hitting and standing, and their strategy may vary. To make it more complex, more kinds of modifications can be considered, and some assumptions can be discarded (like considering the change in player strategy with the rule modification). With more ways of rule modifications, fairness can be controlled better. There is still many things to be discovered.

References

[Mu20] Zhao Mu. Continuous blackjack: Equilibrium, deviation and adaptive strategy. *arXiv*, 2020.

- [RRB56] Herbert Maisel & James P. McDermott Roger R. Baldwin, Wilbert E. Cantey. The optimum strategy in blackjack. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 51:429–439, 1956.
- [Wor18] et al. Worley, Skyler. Blackjack player choice, superstition, and calculated odds of winning. 2018.